

THE IMPORTANCE OF SIMULATION TRAINING IN PRACTICAL LESSONS

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Objectives: to increase students' interest in their specialty, develop the ability to independently and effectively solve problems in the field of professional activity, and test the professional readiness of the future specialist for independent work.

Materials and methods: simulators and phantoms, virtual patients, groups of students, medical records.

Results: the Department of Clinical Simulation conducts practical classes in the discipline "Internal Medicine" for 3-5 year students based on simulation training.

Unlike conventional classroom conditions, simulators allow the student to experience extreme situations, allow him to think independently and actively, rather than passively, remember information. Modeling methods and technologies, algorithms and standards, simulators and phantoms help students master skills and acquire practical skills in the form of automatism . The simulation process can create a pre-training environment that allows existing clinical instruments and consumables to be used in a "real world" environment, in real time.

At the training stage, 3rd-4th year students repeat and improve methods of examining patients in normal and pathological conditions by organs and systems (palpation of the lungs and heart, percussion, auscultation, blood pressure measurement). Students will also have the opportunity to learn ECG recording and change analysis skills.

5th year students learn to formulate a diagnosis and provide practical assistance in emergency situations, adapted to real situations based on the training "A patient comes to see a doctor."

Conclusions:

1. Training with the help of simulators is one of the effective teaching methods in the formation of professional qualifications and the development of practical skills of undergraduate students at medical universities.

2. Correct organization of the practice process using simulation technologies makes it possible to acquire professional practical skills at a higher level than the theoretical description.

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